

Flower pigments : Flavonoid glycoside from *Peltophorum inernis*

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Chemical investigation of the flowers of *Peltophorum inernis* (Syn. *peltophorum ferruginenn*; Leguminosae) resulted in the isolation (0.5%) of a flavonoid glucoside m.p. 221–23°. It gave a positive cyanidin test¹ both in acid as well as in alkali media. A negative Wilson boric acid test² proved it to be a flavanone glycoside. Absorption λ_{max}^{EtOH} 285 m μ and 306 sh. m μ . Specific rotation : 0.304 gm. subst., 25 ml. acetone, 1 dm. tube; $\alpha_D = 41.4^\circ$.

The glycoside on hydrolysis gave an aglycone, colourless needles (alcohol and benzene), m.p. 247–48° (lit.³ 248). The aglycone was characterized as narnigenin by R_f value, co-chromatography, melting and mixed melting points and also by U.V. and n.m.r. data, the U.V. absorption : λ_{max}^{EtOH} 288, 315 sh.m μ . N.M.R. (CD_3COCD_3) : triplet 2.85 (2H) at C_3 ; quartet 5.41 (1H) at C_2 ; singlet 5.95 (2H) at C_6 and C_8 ; doublet 6.85 (2H) at C_5 and C_7 ; doublet 7.35 (2H) at C_2 and C_8 . The aglycone gave an acetate, m.p. 125–26° (lit.³ 126).

The hydrolysate on chromatographic examination showed the presence of glucose as carbohydrate moiety. Complete methylation of the glycoside followed by hydrolysis gave a product m.p. 188–90°⁴ (alcohol). The partial methyl ether was characterized as 7-hydroxy, di-methoxy narnigenin by mixed melting point with an authentic sample.

The glycoside has thus been proved to be a narnigenin-7-glucoside.

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